

The Counterintuitive-ness of Quantum Mechanics: A Short Summary of Current Interpretations

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“Reality is Only Intuitive to Us Because We Think We Understand it.”

Introduction

Any flip of a coin has only two possible outcomes: heads or tails. This is because since a coin has only 2 sides it is a binary system or *Bernoulli trial* that when flipped needs to land on either its “heads” side or its “tails” side. Before said coin is flipped it cannot be described as having landed on its heads side or tails side, since it of course has not yet been flipped. However, once the coin is flipped and lands on one side or the other it can only ever be described as having landed on “heads” or “tails” but not both simultaneously. This concept of systems only being able to exist in “one state or the other at one time” seems to be intuitive. Obviously, the reason for this intuition is because classically this is the way things work. Coin flips can only result in heads or tails, cats can only be dead or alive and a person can only be sleeping or awake but not both at the same.

However what if our intuition isn’t necessarily indicative of the way that things actually work? After all the only reason that things are “intuitive” at all is because they have been learned to be such a way. For example, if there was a man from the twelfth century who time travelled to 2022 and tried a telephone for the first time, the person might actually confuse the voices on the telephone as being nearby. In fact the man might even yell “stop this trick I know that you’re there” helplessly scouring his environment thinking that someone was trying to trick him into believing that the phone was a “magical device”. Of course this is because the world that the twelfth century man knew was vastly different - one where voices could only communicate when in proximity to one another. Therefore it would be understandably insane to think that anything else was possible. After all, science to the twelfth century man seemed established; he did not know about electromagnetic currents and radio waves but rather only that verbal communication was always governed by locality.

Like the twelfth century man, we are arrogant in our intuitions about the physical world we experience around us. We believe that how the physical world works is intuitive to us only because we base it on our presuppositions. For we expect it to work a certain way because we have seen it work that way. However, like the twelfth century man we do not have perfect knowledge of how the physical universe works. Even the twelfth century man lived in a universe where electromagnetic currents and radio waves existed; he just didn’t know it! Similarly, our claim to having figured out “how our universe works” is based only on the knowledge that we currently have and not the knowledge that exists. For like the twelfth century man there may be fundamental truths as to how the universe works that evade our intuition.

The Double Slit Experiment and Quantum Mechanics

An example of one such counterintuitive property of reality has to do with quantum mechanics and superposition. For up until the twentieth century it was assumed that - like coin flips, any binary system in general needed to only exist in a single possible state at once but not both simultaneously. After all, how could a coin land both on “heads” and “tails” at the same time?

Despite their intuitions, early twentieth century experiments such as the famous “Double Slit Experiments” and also “Mach Zender Interferometer” utilizing experiments showed that unlike in classical systems where coins can only exist on one side at a time, subatomic particles could actually exist in “contradicting” states simultaneously at least probabilistically. This phenomenon is entitled “superposition” and is now accepted as a very real property of the very foundation of the physical universe.

However like the twelfth century man and the telephone, when this phenomenon was first discovered it was considered as very counterintuitive. After all how could a subatomic particle be located in two areas of space at once? Surely the subatomic particle needs to be situated either here or there, but not in both places at once! While it is of course true that classical systems like coins do need to work in this way as either being in one state or another but not both simultaneously, quantum systems do not have this restriction. Instead, before quantum systems interact with an outside entity or are “measured” they simply exist in all possible states at once simultaneously and exhibit wave like properties. Such a phenomenon was shown via Young’s double slit experiment which consisted of light being projected through neighboring slits against a screen. When the light hit the screen it formed an interference pattern on the screen which showed that the light was acting as a wave (since interference patterns are produced by different peaks and troughs of the wave interfering with one another).

However as Einstein’s photoelectric effect demonstrated, light needed to not only exist as a wave but also have particle like properties (since Einstein found that the “frequency” of light mattered in relation to its kinetic energy which meant that light needed to be quantized - since it was shown that more “photons” could change kinetic energy thresholds within a system). Once it was shown that light needed to be quantized and therefore have particle like properties as well as wave like properties, it was suggested that perhaps electrons (which at the time were assumed to only have particle like properties) should act as waves as well. Another experiment - Hitachi’s double split experiment was then employed in order to determine if electrons actually acted as waves as well as particles.

In this experiment, a single electron was projected through two slits onto a screen. If the electron was only a particle then it would have needed to simply show up as a single “dot” on the screen. However, the electron formed an interference pattern after traveling through the slits. To the experimenter this made no sense. After all if the electron was a single particle how could it go through both slits at once and form an interference pattern? What was it interfering with? In order to resolve this seeming contradiction, the experimenter placed a detector at each slit to see what was happening to the electron as it went through the slits. However, after the detector was placed and the electron was projected through the slits again it only formed a single dot on the screen as would indicate that it had definitely only traveled through one slit and was therefore just a particle. However, how could the electron go through “both slits at one time” when not measured (as if it was acting as a wave) and then only go through one slit definitively

when measured (as if it was acting like a particle)? Why should the act of measurement change the state of the electron? It was therefore discovered that since subatomic particles such as electrons and photons are in a superposition of states prior to measurement, they only take on a definitive reality when measured and so to speak “forced” to select only one slit.

The Quantum Bomb

One other example of quantum superposition occurs in the “quantum bomb experiment”. In the quantum bomb experiment, a bomb could be detonated by its interaction with a photon. Therefore, if one wanted to know whether a bomb was a dud or not, a photon could simply be fired at the bomb and if it didn’t detonate then obviously it was a dud. The issue is that the detonation of a bomb is obviously very destructive so should be avoided. However, is there a way that the bomb can be known whether to be a dud or not without having to run the risk of actually detonating it?

Such a mechanism could be accomplished using a Mach Zehnder Interferometer. With a Mach Zehnder Interferometer, an experiment could be devised: light can be fired at a beam splitter which directs 50% of the light to an upper path and 50% of the light to a lower path. Additionally, there is a second beam splitter which splits the light a second time. After light is split a second time it is then reflected onto either detector A or detector B. If the two light beams from the upper and lower paths interfere at the second beam splitter and cause “constructive interference” (where the crests and troughs of the wave don’t cancel each other out), then the light is reflected onto detector A. If however the two light beams from the upper and lower paths interfere at the second beam splitter and cause “destructive interference” (where the crests and troughs of the wave do cancel each other out), then the light is reflected onto detector B. When this experiment is conducted, the light can only show up on detector A, since when it undergoes destructive interference it can never actually show up even on detector B.

When a single photon is fired however, since it is only one photon it should only show up on either detector A or B since there is nothing for it to interact with. However, when such an experiment is conducted, the photon only ever shows up on detector A indicating that it had interfered with itself thus always causing destructive interference at B and therefore never actually hitting detector B. The reason for this happening is because the photon exists in a superposition of states and therefore takes both paths and interacts with itself thus always going through the upper path and the lower path. Furthermore, the reason there is a superposition here is because there is never any measurement being done at the detectors. This is because if the photon is in a superposition of states it will always undergo both constructive and destructive interference with itself and therefore only ever show up on detector A (because of constructive interference) yet never show up on detector B since it had destructively interfered with itself prior to hitting that detector. This shows how when there is no act of measurement the photon does in fact exist in a superposition of states and takes both the lower and upper paths.

Now this experiment could be redone but with a bomb placed in the lower path. If the bomb is a dud then no matter what path the photon takes it would still not be detonated. Therefore it’s as if there was no bomb at all thus causing the original superposition to be maintained and the photon to always only hit detector A. However, if there was a live bomb on the lower path, then

if the photon takes the lower path it will surely cause the bomb to detonate. Therefore if the photon hits the lower path it could never actually show up on any of the detectors let alone interfere with itself. When such an experiment was conducted (simulated but obviously not with bombs), the photon did exist in a superposition of states when the bomb was a dud always going through detector A. However, when the bomb was live, if the photon took the lower path(50% of the time) then it detonated the bomb and never showed up on any of the detectors. If however, the photon took the upper path then half the time it hit detector A and half the time it hit detector B. The reason this is so surprising is because if the bomb is live, even if the photon never actually hits the bomb, 25% of the time it will show up on detector B. This is compared to when the bomb is a dud, the photon never showing up on detector B (since the superposition is maintained). This is because if the bomb is live then obviously it would be known that the photon took the lower path thus constituting a measurement and therefore causing the photon to not be in a superposition of states and never undergo the upper route. If the photon goes through the upper path however information about the bomb being a dud or not is never known so the photon maintains its superposition. This shows how superposition is maintained any time there is uncertainty relating to which way the photon travelled and ultimately shows that such a superposition only “breaks” upon measurement. What is incredible here is that it shows how a bomb could be probabilistically determined as a “dud” or a “live bomb” without every truly being measured. For the bomb is never weighed, purposefully detonated or “broken up” in any way, instead it is static and has its state probabilistically determined only because it may or may not break a quantum superposition.

It is this counterintuitive principle of measurement breaking superpositions that defines the physical universe at a quantum level. This of course is unlike what is considered as the “more intuitive” classical world where systems such as coin flips only could exist in one definitive state at once and never in simultaneous superposition like states. Furthermore classical systems don’t seem to depend on contextual measurement in order to take on definitive states but rather seem to have pre-determined states despite any measurement made upon them. Of course these ideas are only intuitive because humans interact with the physical universe at a classical level and not at a quantum level. For if humans interacted with the universe at a quantum level, classic positional constraints like “coin flips only landing on one side or the other” would be considered counterintuitive.

Interpretations of Quantum Mechanics

Per quantum mechanics, subatomic particles can be described by “wave functions” or mathematical tools that convey all of the information known about a quantum particle prior to measurement (since these quantum particles are “waves” before measured). Such information can then be used to “predict” probabilities for a quantum particles measured definitive finite state. For example, if before an electron is measured it is said to be in a superposition of states of angular momentum where it is both “spinning up” and “spinning down” simultaneously, then such an electrons wave function can be used to describe how likely it is that the electron will eventually be measured as a “spin up” electron or a “spin down” electron.

Such a wave function is mathematically defined by the “Schrodingers equation” that describes the evolution of a quantum state (such as an electron) through time. The Schrodinger

equation could be used to attain the probabilities of which states a subatomic particle will “collapse” into. The probability of such a particle’s collapsed position can be attained by squaring the amplitude of its probability wave in a particular point of space. This means that the higher the squared amplitude of a wave function at a particular point in space is, the higher the probability is that the particle that is in a superposition will become measured at that point in space. Now despite this wave function evolving according to the Schrodinger equation, once it is actually measured it seemingly “collapses” since the state of the particle goes from having a “multiple possible states at once” to only the one definitive state it is measured as.

Now the actual process as to how “measurement” causes the superposition of states of a subatomic particle to seemingly “collapse” into real definitive states is hotly debated. While there are many models that seek to explain the phenomenon, 3 of the most common interpretations are the “Copenhagen interpretation”, “Hidden Variables Theories” and the “Many Worlds interpretation”.

The Copenhagen Interpretation

The Copenhagen interpretation was developed by Niels Bohr and Werner Heisenberg and simply insists that a particles mathematical wave function “collapses” upon measurement into one definitive state because its superposition is actually broken. This interpretation purports that a particles wave function collapses in accordance with the “Born Rule” (that assigns a probability of definitive eigenstates upon collapse as according with a squared result of the wave function’s amplitude at a specific point in space). It also therefore views such a collapse as “probabilistic” but also inherently indeterministic. So for example, if a measurer measures an electrons wave function, prior to that measurement the electron exists in a superposition of states with a wide probabilistic wave function, but upon measurement such a wave function instantaneously “collapses” into only “definitive state”(per a calculation of difference in potential eigenstates/ $\sqrt{2}$). Therefore, when one “measures” a particle, the particle needs to develop “finite” properties because its super positive wave function has “collapsed” due to the measurement by the measurer. The Copenhagen interpretations has many variations but essentially proposes that quantum mechanics is inherently “indeterministic” and “wave functions” finitely collapse upon interaction with a measurer outside the quantum system.

The Many Worlds Interpretation

The Many Worlds interpretation first proposed by Hugh Everett argues that probabilistic wave functions never “collapse” but instead *split* into individual branches entitled “worlds” per every possible state of the superimposed quantum system. So for example, when measuring an electrons quantum system thats in a superposition of “spinning up” and “spinning down”, the wave function never “collapses” objectively into just one definitive state but rather splits in accordance with the Schrodingers equation and therefore branches into “multiple worlds” where in one world the electron is measured as spin up and in another would the electron is measured as spin down.

The reason that it seems like the wave function “collapses” is because observers would only exist on one specific branch after the measurement and therefore wouldn’t be able to interact with all

of the other branches that still “exist”. For in reality all “branches” of the wave function are merely all part of one “universal wave function” that includes all potential branches of every wave function. However to an observer who measures a quantum system since they only exist on one branch of the wave function they would never see any of the other branches. The Many Worlds interpretation is deterministic in the sense that there is no “randomness” needed as to which potential states of the quantum system will actually exist since every time a wave function seems to “collapse” they all still exist simultaneously.

The mechanism as to how such multiple “worlds” become branched upon the measurement of a system involves “entanglement” and “decoherence”.

Entanglement and Decoherence

Entanglement is the process of how two interacting subatomic particles take on correlational states. So for example if one larger particle with a spin of “0” is broken down into particles - one with spin -1 and another with spin +1, the two particles are said to be entangled. This is to say that before measurement both particles would exist in a superposition of both spin states. Upon measurement however, if one particle was measured as spin (+1), then the other particle would NEED to be spin (-1) (without even being measured) as the two are entangled and need to together have spins that add up to 0. The interesting part here is that it is said that both particles exist in a superposition of states prior to measurement so it is not merely that one particle was always spin (+1) and the other was always spin (-1), but rather that both were actually spin (+1 & -1 superimposed). Only upon measurement did one particle “probabilistically” become spin +1 which therefore “transformed” the other particle as well out of its “dependent superposition” into spin -1.

Physicists Einstein, Podolsky and Rosen famously had a problem with entanglement since they believed that apparent quantum “instantaneous communication” between the two particles happened at faster than the speed of light and therefore violated the theory of special relativity (which proposed that information could never travel faster than light). Therefore, they insisted that in reality the two particles were always spin+1 or spin-1 but merely had their states revealed upon measurement, which implied that no superposition was ever present. However, John Stewart Bell eventually proved (or at least has been thought to prove) that Einstein, Podolsky and Rosen were wrong that the particle’s states finitely existed and were merely “hidden” prior to measurement. Instead through a series of experiments on the correlational states of entangled particles, Bell proved that such particles were actually superimposed and only actually took on their definitive states of +1 and -1 upon measurement (with the assumption of statistical independence). Therefore, when one particle is measured, that particles superposition collapses into one definitive state which also instantaneously makes the other particles superposition collapse into always the opposing state. Once the particles are connected it can therefore be said that their wave functions become “correlated” in how they are definitively measured. Note that this actually does not allow faster than light information being transmitted as it would still take slower than light communication to ever “convey” such information about entangled particle states.

A measurer is essentially just a complex quantum system themselves. Therefore, when a measurer measures another quantum system such as an electron, they actually interact and become “entangled” with that electron. Therefore, the reason why the electron appears to have “definitive” properties upon measurement is because the observer becomes entangled with the electron when measured which essentially causes their two wave functions to combine into a single broad complex wave function.

This is why to the observer, the electron needs to be in only one state or the other since the 2 are a part of a broader wave function where everything within that function can't “notice” each others superpositions since they are now existing within the same superposition. In this way, the 2 have become situated on the same “branch” or “world” of the wave function when entangled. Since they are in the same world, the other possible states for the electron still exist but are now outside the “entangled branch” of the observer. Furthermore, the entanglement of the observer with the quantum system of the electron essentially causes a cascade of entanglement entitled decoherence where if enough things become entangled, piecing together their original superpositions becomes impossible due to the volume of the entanglements. Therefore, instead of the wave function “collapsing” into one definitive state, the many worlds interpretation suggests that it actually “expands” to include both the observer and the electron. It is rather only from the observers perspective that the electron is definitive since the observer is confined to the same branch of the wave function as the electron due to them interacting, becoming entangled and therefore becoming part of the same wave function.

This is to say that once the observer measures the electron, the two are entangled become both part of the same wave function and therefore become both part of the same “superposition” of states. Therefore, the observer can no longer “see” the superposition of the electron since the observer is now a part of that superposition! This combination of the observer and the electron essentially cause the “broader wave function” to branch into separate wave function, where each branch consists of one possible way in which they interacted. Therefore, if the observer measures the electrons spin, then there will be two branches formed in the wave function - one branch where the electron is measured as spin down and another where the electron is measured as spin up. However to the observer, the electron will only be in one state or the other since the observer now needs to be on one of the two branches along with the electron. That being said, there would be other branches where the observer exists along with the electron measured in a different state, yet from the perspective of the observer, this branch would not be able to be interacted with. The superposition of the electron however still exists but is now combined to include the superposition of the observer as well since the two have become entangled. In this way, to an outside observer the two will essentially be in a “combined superposition” since the outside observer is not in the branch with them.

Therefore unlike in the Copenhagen interpretation, the many worlds interpretation essentially suggests that the wave function does not collapse but rather combine to include both the observer and the particle being measured. Furthermore, the two become part of the same superposition and such a superposition never “breaks”.

Integrating “Entropy” With Quantum Mechanics

When a quantum system becomes entangled with multiple other quantum systems at once, they all become part of the same wave function. This process of multiple entanglements occurring from the perspective of a single quantum system essentially defines the quantum systems "world". For the "real world" to the quantum system is essentially just everything that it is "entangled with". Therefore, the number of "entanglements" from the perspective of a single quantum system can be measured as the amount of information in that "quantum systems" world. Anytime there is a larger number of entanglements, there will be more information within the quantum system. For example, if the quantum system consists of an electron entangled with only 1 other electron then there is not a lot of information that can be gained from knowing the state of the quantum system. Observing the spin of the first electron will tell you instantly the spin of the second electron. However, if there is a much larger quantum system with many more entanglements, then obviously there would be a lot more information one would need to know to surmise the spin of one of its quantum particles. For if in a quantum system consisting of 2 entangled pairs there are only 2 particles state that can be configured, then in a larger system with many entanglements there can be many many more configurations. Per the classic definition of "shannon entropy", anytime there is a larger number of configurations of systems states, the system in question exhibits a higher informational "entropy". Therefore, since when there are more entanglements there are many more informational configurations there is also more informational "entropy".

Since all entangled particles share a wave function with one another, the more entangled particles present in a quantum system the larger the wave function will be. When there are many and many entanglements between particles, the wave function grows larger and larger and can no longer be "realized" by any observer. This cascade of entanglements is known as decoherence since a quantum system seemingly "decoheres" to an observer since it has too much entanglement to now have any of its individual states "discoverable". In reality however it is not that the wave function of 2 particles collapses upon observation, but rather that it is expanding. Using this logic, when decoherence happens the entropy of the quantum system grows larger and larger since now it is impossible to access the entirety of the quantum wave function. Furthermore, according to the many worlds interpretation, the total wave function would result in "branches" of worlds that actually make it so that the observers branch will be unable to interact with other branches.

If entanglements between quantum systems can be likened to strings then it would be nearly impossible to "untie" trillions and trillions of strings. This is why quantum effects in larger classical systems are not apparent - not because the quantum effects don't exist at larger scales, but rather because at larger scales the entanglement "entropies" are far too high and "disordered". In a quantum system however with a small number of entangled particles the quantum system is still said to be "coherent" because there is still a small enough measure of entanglements and therefore information where the individual effects of entanglements are "apparent".

Entanglement and Locality

One interesting theory that has been put forth states that such "webs" of entanglements could be responsible for the physical universe as it appears to exist. Since nearby quantum particles

become “entangled” when they are physically near one another, perhaps it can be said that - it is not a relation of locality between two quantum system that governs entanglements, but rather it is a relation of entanglements that governs locality. This would essentially mean that there is no “*ontic*” space that exists but rather just a wave function consisting of entangled quantum particles. When quantum particles are highly ‘entangled’ with many other quantum particles, that suite of quantum particles can be translated as being ‘near’ one another in space. This building of “space” out of entanglements develops a model of “emergent spacetime” often popularized by a subset of theoretical physicists such as Sean Carroll. Additionally, per this theory vibrations in the quantum fields that permeate the universe would result in energy which “breaks” such entanglements. Therefore it can be said that energy is higher when there are “less” entanglements. Empty “spaces” would therefore said to be composed of “extremely entangled” quantum states since they would have less energy.

Of course if no ontic “space” exists the question then becomes how any quantum systems can become “entangled” in the first place. For if space is only a result of entangled quantum systems where and how do any quantum systems first become entangled? This is to say that if quantum systems as wave functions are “real things” then don’t these “real things” need a space in which to exist? In quantum mechanics such an imagined space of “wave functions” is known as “hilbert space”. Hilbert space is a mathematical space where wave functions exist as vectors. This wouldn’t be a physical space experienced by observers but rather a Mathematical space of wave functions.

Differences Between Interpretations In Terms of Wave Functions

There is therefore much debate as to what “quantum mechanics” implies about the nature of reality. According to the Copenhagen interpretation, a measurer is needed to “collapse” super-positive wave functions into definitive states. This “collapse” of the wave function would define fundamental reality and render “measurers” as having “real roles” in the collapse of wave function and thereby the existence of physical reality (note that measurers here don’t mean consciousnesses necessarily but any system that interacts with a quantum system). The many worlds interpretation however assumes that no “collapse” ever occurs, but rather only seems to occur from the perspective of an observer. When the wave function seems to collapse it is actually only branching and the observer will always only find themselves in one particular branch thus making it seem to them as if the wave function collapsed into a definitive finite state when in reality it still exists as a superposition of other states in different branches. Most interpretations in general though do seem to acknowledge the existence of a “probabilistic superposition” (by means of a wave function), out of which reality finitely evolves.

Hidden Variable Theories

Some physicists such as Albert Einstein did however famously have trouble accepting the “probabilistic” nature of quantum mechanics altogether and instead insisted that such uncertainties are the results of hidden variables in experiments. For example perhaps in the double slit experiment, the seemingly non-local results of the state of the particle going through the slits are simply explained by “hidden variables” within the quantum system instead of wave function collapse. Physicist David Bohm for example popularized such a theory where “pilot

waves” guided the waves of light to different positions through the slits. According to Bohm, the exact areas of the projector that “pilot” these waves however are difficult to measure and therefore how exactly they differ in the projection of waves is “hidden” to experimenters. This would mean that the particles and waves both exist but are difficult to measure. While John Stewart Bell did prove that in the case of entanglement, nonlocal correlations could not be the result of hidden variables, he also assumed statistical independence. Statistical independence is the assumption that all measurements are random prior to an experiment from the context of an observer. However, if it was assumed that the entire universe was “superdeterministic” in that the nonlocal correlations between particles were actually the result of every aspect of the universe being correlated BECAUSE in actuality the whole universe is a deterministic conspiracy where all possible fates are already decided, then hidden variables would then again be possible. For if everything was “inherently fully predetermined” and not random, then a particle state correlating with the measurers state wouldn’t be surprising! It would rather simply be because the universe is deterministic in a time independent manner where the two would always have been correlated to have such an interaction that way. Furthermore, obviously if it was claimed that the universe is “superdeterministic” then such hidden variable theories could not be disproved. While there are many different versions of “hidden variable theories”, superdeterminism does require the existence of “statistical dependence” which somewhat “biases” the assumptions of every independent scientific experiment which by definition are meant to rely on randomness. That being said, perhaps such “randomness” can still seemingly exist at an experimental level while also “not actually existing” when taking into context the entire universe.

Conclusion

Interpretations of quantum mechanics (IE - the measurement problem, entanglement etc) are needed simply because quantum mechanics was “discovered” after classical mechanics. Perhaps if classical mechanics was discovered second to quantum mechanics then it would be classical mechanics that was considered as counterintuitive. However, since science relies on reductionism, quantum mechanics only became relevant when it was possible to “break down” and reduce classical matter into its tiniest quantum components.

Furthermore what the study of quantum mechanics shows is that at a small enough and simplistic enough scale, individual systems rely on the context of outside systems and are not indeed inherently objectively independent. Whether this “contextual dependence” is due to superdeterminism, wave function collapse, branching “worlds” or something else entirely is up for debate. However what is not up for debate is that since quantum iota make up the essential “components” of all classical iota, quantum mechanics is indeed how things “actually work” as opposed to how larger classical things “seem to work”.